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Reuse of recovered glass-fiber from printed circuit boards: production and characterization of eco-friendly molding compounds

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Abstract: Ore materials are becoming scarce and the use of recycled materials onto the manufacturing process of the composites are becoming more important. The recycling process of molding compounds (MC) are difficult to proceed due to their characteristics. In this work, instead of recycling the MC, recycled material, namely recovered fibers, were included in the manufacturing process. These recovered fibers came from waste printed circuit boards (WPCB), treated in a previous step of this project by a solid-liquid process, organic swelling. To each MC, three possible formulations are proposed: one with partial use of long fiber, another with powder fiber mixed with fiber glass and one with full percentage of long fiber from WPCB. This procedure separates the fiber layer and without contaminants. To evaluate the influence of using WPCB fibers, mechanical tests were performed: flexural, tensile and Charpy strength. The aim it's to compare the formulations with recycled material with the original one and evaluate which formulation has the best mechanical qualities and possible environmental-friendly alternative. According to the results, the more efficient way to use the recovered fibers would be in a smaller fraction and coarse aggregate so that it can maintain its normal mechanical characteristics and slightly improve it.

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1. Introduction

According to Global E-Waste Monitor [1], about 53.6 Mt of E-Waste were generated in 2019 which can be translated into 7.3 kg per capita. E-Waste can be divided into six categories, but in all of them have one component in common: printed circuit boards (PCB). PCB are used to mechanically support and electrically connect electronic components using conductive pathways, tracks or signal traces etched from copper sheets laminated onto a non-conductive substrate, and so this PCB have a lot of metals and ore material that can be recovered.

A previous work made by other part of the project developed an eco-friendly process to recycle PCB and divided them into several ore materials, to be again introduced in the chain value. The recycling process was based on a solid-liquid separation using a organic solvent, N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone. This separation is called an organic solvent. From this process, PCB are delaminated and separated into three parts: copper sheets, glass-fiber and gold fingers (in the connecting terminals parts of the PCB). Since the aim of this work is to reuse and/or reintroduce all the recovered materials from PCB, the only material left is the glass-fiber.

To bridge the last part of the project this present work has the main goal of reintroducing the recovered fibers in molding compounds, since they can be used in a large type of areas, and it is a glass-fiber reinforced thermoset polymers (as the resin used in the production of PCB).

2. Methodology

2.1. Recovered glass-fibers characterization

The recovered fibers are a coarse aggregate of size approximately 1,52:0,81:0,48 mm and to evaluate the effect of the size of the aggregate, the recovered fibers were turn into a fine aggregate. Figure 1 shows both the coarse and fine aggregate.

Fig. 1. Recovered fibers from WPCB in coarse (left side) and fine aggregate (right side).

The characteristics of the recovered fibers were determined by two analyses: thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and a Fourier Transformation Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). TGA was done using NETZSCH STA 449 F3 under nitrogen atmosphere with a flow rate of 20 mL per minute and a scan rate of 10 K/min over a temperature range of 30°C to 1200 °C. A test sample of 5 mg was used for each run and FTIR was performed on a BRUKER Compact FT-IR Spectrometer in the region of IR-medium (4000-500 cm⁻¹).

2.2. Molding Compounds formulations

Two types of molding compounds were formulated: Bulk Molding Compounds (BMC) and Dough Molding Compound based in epoxy resin (DMC). In which one, different quantities of Non-Metallic Fraction (NMF) fibers were used instead of common glass-fiber. The differences between all the formulations are explicit in Table 1.

Table 1. Percentages of different types of glass-fiber (recovered fibers in powder and coarse aggregate and raw glass-fibers) included in each formulation.

	Recovered NMF – powder (%)	Recovered NMF (%)	Glass-fiber (%)
BMC_0	0	0	100
BMC_1	0	25	75
BMC_2	25	0	75
BMC_3	0	100	0
DMC_0			100
DMC_1		25	100
DMC_2	25		100

As a result, eight plates of 210 x 210 x 2 mm³ of BMCs were obtained, shown in figure 1 from a) to d). The DMCs, figure 2 e) to g), resulted in six plates of 210 x 210 x 2 mm. Subsequently, specimens for tensile, flexural, and Charpy impact testing were cut from the plates. In the case of tensile specimens, 150 x 22 mm² pieces were cut, which were then machined into type 1B dogbone specimens, described in standard ISO 527-4.'

Fig. 2. Molding Compounds formulations a) to d) refers to BMC and e) to g) to DMC formulations

The mechanical tests were performed according to methods described in the following standards: ISO 179:1982 (Charpy impact), ISO 14125 (Flexural) and ISO 527-4 (Tensile).

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Chemical composition analysis of non-metallic fraction

TGA showed that the maximum degradation temperature was obtained at 341.6 °C; this value agrees with the temperature of degradation of the neat composite reported by Li et al, 2010 [2] that stated a maximum degradation

temperature at 343 °C. The TGA evidenced that the thermal properties of the glass-fiber remained identical after the organic swelling.

The principal band is 934,72 cm⁻¹, between C-H bend and C-Br stretch. This high pick and the near section in the spectrum show the main bands: C-H bend, C-Br stretch and C=O stretch. Since it's an brominate epoxy resin who constitutes the WPCB, it's expected that C-Br stretch it's one of the main bends. The other main ones are also predictable because the resin it's an organic component.

Fig. 3 Thermogravimetric analysis of PCB non-metallic in powder (left side) and Infrared spectrum of PCB non-metallic in powder (right side).

3.2. Mechanical properties

In terms of mechanical properties, Table 1 resumes all the results: Charpy impact, flexural and tensile strength. Result analyses were made by comparing (in percentual terms) all test series for BMC and DMC to the first one (BMC_0 and DMC_0) that didn't have any recycled compound added to it.

Table 2. Percentage of improvement on Charpy impact test, flexural strength and modulus and tensile strength and modulus, comparing to original formulations

Test Series	Charpy Impact	Flexural Strength	Flexural Modulus	Tensile of Strength	Tensile Modulus
BMC_1	28,30%	1,28%	5,27%	1,34%	-6,57%
BMC_2	27,47%	-6,07%	-4,95%	-3,46%	-19,87%
BMC_3	87,64%	-26,95%	-41,00%	-29,74%	-27,60%
DMC_1	6,57%	-12,20%	-15,80%	175,72%	155,22%
DMC_2	-23,91%	-13,05%	-17,02%	230,27%	182,64%

4. Conclusions

In partnership with other team of the project, a new and eco-friendly recycling process was design to WPCB and the last ore material needed to be reused, in order to close the loop of all the process. As the chemical analysis showed, the thermo properties of the fibbers stayed intact and only a small fraction of the organic solvent remained in the coarse. This showed to be a good result because all the formulations produced adsorbed higher amount of energy.

Although the results did not show an overall improvement of all mechanical properties, a new way to reintroduce recovered glass-fiber was found but it must be applied to different types of areas, depending on what type of mechanical properties improved.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRediT author statement

Márcia AD Silva: Data curation, Software; Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Raimundo Silva:** Methodology, Data curation, Software. **P.J.R.O Nóvoa:** Methodology, Data curation, Software; Formal analysis, Resources, Supervision. **Helena M.V.M. Soares:** Conceptualisation, Supervision. **Margarida Bastos:** Conceptualisation. **António T. Marques:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Supervision

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